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Sources of Uncertainty in the Realisation of the Triple Point of Water at MSL

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Abstract

This report describes the factors affecting MSL's realisation of the triple point of water. The purpose of the report is to aid in the development of technical procedures, provide the basis for uncertainty analyses, and identify areas for further research. The expanded uncertainty in the realisation of the triple-point temperature is estimated to be in the range 20 μK to 30 μK for the five cells identified as the national standard for the CCT-K7 international comparison. In use, the expanded uncertainty will be about 50 μK due to the additional and dominant uncertainty in the measurements of SPRT resistance.

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1 Introduction

The triple point of water (TPW) is the defining point on both the thermodynamic scale and ITS-90 [1]. Ideally, it is the equilibrium temperature of three pure phases: ice, water and water vapour. In practice, real triple-point cells suffer from a number of impurity, isotope and pressure effects that tend to depress the realised temperature. In addition, instrumental effects due to the standard platinum resistance thermometer (SPRT) and resistance bridge have an influence on the uncertainty. Figure 1 summarises all of the known influence variables.

Figure 1: A diagram summarising the sources of uncertainty in a water-triple-point measurement.

The following sections describe the physical effects of the various influences and estimate the corrections and uncertainties introduced by the effects. The effects may be classified as isotopic effects, pressure effects, impurity effects, and instrumental effects due to the SPRT and the resistance bridge.

2 Isotopic Effects

2.1 Background

The Supplementary Information to the ITS-90 [2] requires the water in triple-point cells to have substantially the isotopic composition of ocean water. Uncertainty due to the isotopic composition of the water in triple-point cells arises for several reasons [3-7]:

- Variations in the isotopic composition of sea water. Triple-point temperature variations due to natural isotopic variations in seawater are a few microkelvin so have little practical effect on the realisation of the kelvin. Further, the international science community, through the International Atomic Energy Agency, uses a defined Standard Mean Ocean Water (SMOW) as a point of reference for studies in the isotopic composition of waters. It is assumed here that SMOW satisfies the requirements of the triple point definition and will therefore be used as the point of reference.
- The water used for the manufacture of most TPW cells is continental surface (fresh) water, which for most parts of the World is depleted in the heavy isotopes of hydrogen and oxygen. The typical equivalent temperature depression ranges up to 50 μK or so.
- During the manufacture of TPW cells, distillation further depletes the water of heavy isotopes. This may be partly compensated by enrichment that occurs during degassing.
- When a TPW cell is used, water and ice coexist in the cells and there is some fractionation of isotopes between the two phases.

2.2 Correction for isotopic composition of the water

It is assumed that the heavy isotopes are dilute, so that the isotopic effects are linear with mole fraction and there is no interaction between the different isotopes. Hence the influence of variations in the isotope concentrations on the triple-point temperature can be described by:

$$T_{\text{meas}} = T_{\text{V-SMOW}} + A_{\text{D}}\delta\text{D} + A_{17\text{O}}\delta^{17}\text{O} + A_{18\text{O}}\delta^{18}\text{O}, \quad (1)$$

where $T_{\text{V-SMOW}} = 273.16\text{K}$ by definition, and the delta values represent the departures of the concentrations of the heavy isotopes from those of Vienna-SMOW (a standard reference material used to represent SMOW) and are given by

$$\delta^{18}\text{O} = \left[\frac{(^{18}\text{O}/^{16}\text{O})_{\text{sample}} - (^{18}\text{O}/^{16}\text{O})_{\text{V-SMOW}}}{(^{18}\text{O}/^{16}\text{O})_{\text{V-SMOW}}} \right], \quad (2)$$

with similar definitions for δD and $\delta^{17}\text{O}$. Absolute measurements of the isotope ratios for V-SMOW give

$$(\text{D}/^1\text{H})_{\text{V-SMOW}} = 0.000\ 155\ 76(5),$$

$$(^{18}\text{O}/^{16}\text{O})_{\text{V-SMOW}} = 0.002\ 005\ 20(45),$$

and

$$(^{17}\text{O}/^{16}\text{O})_{\text{V-SMOW}} = 0.000\ 379\ 9(8).$$

The A_i coefficients of (1) are those recommended by White *et al* [3,4] based on Kiyosawa's values [8] for the D and ^{18}O depression constants

$$\begin{aligned}
A_D &= 628 \pm 3 \text{ } \mu\text{K}, \\
A_{^{18}\text{O}} &= 641 \pm 3 \text{ } \mu\text{K}, \\
A_{^{17}\text{O}} &= 57 \pm 1 \text{ } \mu\text{K}.
\end{aligned}
\tag{3}$$

The total uncertainty in the correction for cells is typically less than 1 μK . Corrections for MSL's cells are based on these constants and the measurements of isotopic composition carried out by the Institute for Geological and Nuclear Sciences, Lower Hutt.

2.3 Uncertainty due to fractionation of the water when in use

When the cell is in use, heavy isotopes are fractionated between the ice and water phases. For Deuterium the fractionation factor is 1.02, and for ^{18}O the factor is 1.003, so the most marked effect is for the deuterium. When the cell is in use the ice becomes enriched in deuterium with respect to the water. Thus, the concentration of deuterium in the liquid when the cell is frozen, $[D]_{\text{frac}}$, varies with frozen fraction F according to

$$(1 - F)[D]_{\text{frac}} + 1.02F[D]_{\text{frac}} = [D].$$

where $[D]$ is the deuterium concentration in the unfrozen cell. Hence

$$[D]_{\text{frac}} = \frac{[D]}{1 + 0.02F}.$$

Since deuterium is responsible for about 628 μK of the isotope effect, the change in temperature with frozen fraction can be estimated as

$$\Delta T = 628 \times 0.02F \text{ } \mu\text{K}.\tag{4}$$

For typical frozen fractions between 10% and 40% the triple-point temperature is depressed by between 1 μK and 5 μK below that of a cell with uniform distribution of isotopes. It is assumed that the definition applies to equilibrium fractionation so the effect contributes only uncertainty to the realisation of the triple point. It will be assumed that a cell with 25% frozen fraction conforms to the definition and therefore the water-ice fractionation leads only to an expanded uncertainty of $\pm 2 \text{ } \mu\text{K}$.

3 Pressure Effects

3.1 Background

In a practical TPW cell only a very small fraction of the water at the top of the thermometer well is in close thermal contact with the other two phases (ice and vapour). In effect, the ideal TPW cell is a pressure-controlled ice point, with the pressure at the surface of the water equal to the triple-point pressure. The water around the re-entrant well of the TPW cell comes to equilibrium with the ice mantle (i.e. the melting point) at a pressure that increases with depth of water. The

sensitivity of the melting point of water to pressure can be measured directly but it is more accurately determined from the Clapeyron relation:

$$\frac{dT}{dP} = \frac{T\Delta V}{L}, \quad (5)$$

where ΔV is the change in volume on melting and L is the latent heat. The ITS-90 specifies that $dT/dP = -7.5$ mK per standard atmosphere, which is equal to -730 $\mu\text{K}/\text{m}$ of water.

There are three pressure related effects that alter the temperature measured in the thermometer well.

3.2 Correction and uncertainty due to hydrostatic pressure

The depth of the water in MSL's current set of cells varies from 250 mm to 280 mm. The SPRT sensing elements are also finite in length. The distance from the tip of the SPRT sheath to the centre of the sensing element varies from 20 mm to 30 mm. That is, the mean immersion depth of the SPRTs in use is about $240 \text{ mm} \pm 25 \text{ mm}$. Thus, for cells where the actual hydrostatic head is not measured, the hydrostatic pressure correction is $175 \mu\text{K} \pm 18 \mu\text{K}$ (95%).

Figure 2 shows the immersion characteristic for an SPRT in one of MSL's cells. Note that the immersion characteristic has two parts. The first at the initial parts of the curve (< -100 mm) has the exponential behaviour expected when there are heat leaks up the stem of the thermometer. The second part (> -100 mm) follows a straight line with a slope given by Equation (5). The immersion curve of Figure 2 therefore establishes that the immersion conditions are sufficient to ensure heat leaks are minimal.

When the head of water is measured with the cell in its frozen condition, the uncertainty is dominated by the uncertainty in the determination of the centre of the thermometer sensor. In this case the uncertainty is about $\pm 4 \mu\text{K}$. Note that for comparisons of TPW cells employing the same SPRT, any errors arising from the poor definition of the centre of the SPRT are expected to be the same for all cells.

Figure 2: The immersion characteristics of SPRT 541 in cell 96/1. The Immersion is measured as the distance above the lowest position of the SPRT. The points show the measurements, the solid line the theoretical result as given by Equation (5).

Procedural issues:

- For the highest accuracy the hydrostatic head should be measured when the cell is frozen.

3.3 Residual air pressure

Because the TPW is pressure sensitive, any residual air pressure in the cell will cause the temperature to be depressed by an amount corresponding to about 7.5 mK per atmosphere.

The residual air pressure can be measured as follows. Figure 3 is a photograph of a triple-point cell tilted to just trap, in one of the seal-off tubes, a bubble of the gases normally above the water in the cell. Figure 4 shows the cell tilted further so that the bubble is compressed by a small head of water.

Figure 3: A triple point cell tilted to trap a bubble in one of the seal-off tubes.

Figure 4: The cell tilted further to compress the bubble. Note that the level of the water in the main body of the cell is a few millimetres higher than the highest point on the bubble.

Measurements of the ratios of the volume of the bubble in the two states and the head of water above the bubble in Figure 4 allow an estimate of the residual air pressure.

For the bubble shown in Figure 3 the pressure is

$$P_1 = P_{\text{water}} + P_{\text{air}},$$

where P_{water} is the partial pressure in the vapour space due to the vapour pressure of the water and P_{air} is the partial pressure of the air in the vapour space. For the bubble in Figure 4 the gas pressure is

$$P_2 = P_{\text{water}} + \frac{V_1}{V_2} P_{\text{air}}.$$

Note that the vapour pressure of the water is the same in the two cases because the temperature of the water is the same in the two cases. For the bubble in Figure 4 pressure is exerted on the bubble by the air above the surface of the water, P_1 , and by the head of water above the bubble. That is

$$P_2 = P_{\text{water}} + \frac{V_1}{V_2} P_{\text{air}} = P_{\text{water}} + P_{\text{air}} + P_{\text{head}}$$

and hence

$$P_{\text{air}} = P_{\text{head}} \left(\frac{V_2}{V_1 - V_2} \right). \quad (6)$$

Note that this measurement can be done independently of the temperature of the water, so long as the temperature is stable during the two measurements of bubble volume. The pressure correction constant due to the head of air is the same as for the hydrostatic head effect, and therefore the temperature error due to the residual air pressure is

$$\Delta T = 0.730 h \left(\frac{V_2}{V_1 - V_2} \right) \text{ mK/m}. \quad (7)$$

where h is the head (in m). The effect of the air pressure is quite small; with a bubble compression factor ($V_1:V_2$) of 2:1 and a head of 40 mm the temperature error is only 30 μK . For most of the cells owned by MSL, the compression factor is about 100:1 and the effect is below 1 μK .

Procedural issues:

- The cell should be allowed to stabilise at room temperature before the measurements and subject to minimal handling during the measurements.
- The head should be measured from the bottom of the meniscus of the main body of water to the bottom of the bubble.
- As the cell is tilted, the bubble will compress in two stages. During the first stage the bubble volume will collapse rapidly as the water vapour condenses, and the level of the water will be almost the same in the bubble as the main body of water – the bubble pressure is dominated by the vapour pressure of the water. In the

second phase, the head will increase steadily as the bubble volume decreases according to the ideal gas law – the bubble pressure is dominated by the partial pressure of the residual air.

- The model excludes the effect of surface tension on the bubble size.

3.4 Pressure effect due to the buoyancy of the ice

The ice, because it floats in the water can exert a buoyancy force on the bottom of the thermometer well. The effect was mentioned briefly by Furukawa and Bigge [9], and is known to others [10], but apparently no model has been published.

If it is assumed that the ice is fully immersed and the force is distributed over an area a of the thermometer tube then the temperature depression induced by the buoyancy force is

$$\Delta T = \frac{730 \text{ Vol}_{\text{ice}} (\rho_{\text{water}} - \rho_{\text{ice}}) g}{a} \mu\text{K} \quad (8)$$

where ρ_{water} and ρ_{ice} are the densities of water and ice (~ 1.00 and 0.92 respectively), and g is the gravitational acceleration. For 200 ml of ice pressing on 10 mm^2 of tube the effect is 1.2 mK. A mitigating factor is that the sensor in the SPRT is not in good thermal contact with the bottom of the well. If it is assumed that the thermal conductivity between the sensor and any part of the ice-water interface is proportional to the area of the outside surface of the thermometer well in close contact with the thermometer, then the fraction of this depression detected by the sensor is a/A where A is the total area of ice-water interface surrounding the sensor. For a purely cylindrical thermometer tube of diameter D and sensor length L the depression sensed by the SPRT is very approximately

$$\Delta T = \frac{730 \text{ Vol}_{\text{ice}} (\rho_{\text{water}} - \rho_{\text{ice}}) g}{\pi D (L + D/2)} \mu\text{K}. \quad (9)$$

For the MSL cells with 25% of the ice frozen and fully immersed, and well diameter of 13 mm and sensor length of 30 mm, the effect is about $8 \mu\text{K}$. Note that the effect may be much less than this if the ice floats freely and is not fully immersed, and may be more than this figure if there is additional lateral pressure due to the spherical or tapered shape of the end of the thermometer tube.

Note that the main benefit of using a sponge at the bottom of the thermometer well, conventionally to protect the thermometer and the well, may be to thermally isolate the thermometer from the effect. It is not known how large the sponge should be.

Figure 5 shows the immersion profile for a cell without a sponge. The rapid fall in temperature as the SPRT reaches the bottom of the thermometer well is presumably due to the buoyancy pressure.

Figure 5: The immersion characteristic of a triple-point cell without the sponge at the bottom of the thermometer well.

Procedural issues

- When using a triple point cell always use the sponge in the bottom of the thermometer well.

4 Impurities

4.1 Background

There are four identifiable groups of impurities that affect the TPW temperature: crystal defects, dissolved gases, ionic impurities, and non-ionic impurities. According to Raoult's law [11] the freezing point of water is depressed by impurities by

$$\Delta T = \frac{RT_f^2}{\Delta H_f} m = K_f m, \quad (10)$$

where R is the gas constant, T_f is the freezing-point temperature, ΔH_f is the latent heat of freezing, and m is the molality of the impurity (moles of solute/kg of solvent). The cryoscopic constant K_f for water is about $1.86 \text{ K} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1} \cdot \text{l}^{-1}$ (equivalent to 0.103 mK per part per million impurity).

4.2 Crystal defects

It is known that the strain effects caused by the freezing of the mantle cause variations of up to several tenths of a millikelvin, although little definite is known of the mechanisms leading to the effects. Most of the effects are relieved as the ice anneals over 3 to 4 days. There is also a possibility of a non-equilibrium concentration of defects in the freshly frozen ice. If the equilibration of the defects takes place at a rate similar to the diffusion time constant in ice (11 days) then a small improvement in the cells can be expected over the one to two weeks after freezing. This is consistent with the observations of Furukawa *et al* at NIST [12] who

concluded that within four days cells agreed to within 100 μK and after 11 days the results agreed within the resolution of the measurements, about 10 μK .

In recent times the cells prepared at MSL have all been frozen using the HART Quickstick[®], a heat pipe based cooling rod. This freezes the cell very slowly ensuring the mantle is crack-free and has relatively low stress so that relaxation times of only 3-4 days are necessary.

It is assumed here that all cells have been aged sufficiently for the ice to anneal and for the defects to equilibrate so the uncertainty is close to zero.

McAllan [13] also discussed the effects of crystal size on the TPW temperature. The effect arises from perturbations to the pressure on the ice due to different surface tension associated with surface curvature. He concluded that the effects are below 10 μK . In any case, the effect would be the same in well-aged cells when the ice crystals become large. Also all triple-point cells have very similar dimensions so any bias should be common to all, and the effect can be considered part of the triple-point definition.

4.3 Total impurity concentration

Possibly the best technique for determining the magnitude of the impurity effects is to plot the temperature versus the melted fraction [14]. This technique exploits the fact that most of the impurities have a low solubility in ice, and therefore as the frozen fraction increases the concentration of the impurities increases and the triple point-temperature is depressed further. The temperature dependence is described by

$$T_{\text{obs}} - T_{\text{pure}} = \frac{-c_0}{AF}. \quad (11)$$

where F is the melted fraction, c_0 is the mole-fraction of the impurity and A is the first cryoscopic constant. By measuring the temperature as the ice freezes and plotting temperature versus $1/F$ it is possible to obtain an estimate of c_0/A from the slope of the line and to use this to estimate the concentration of the impurities.

This has not been done with the MSL cells. However, other checks described below can provide information on the concentration of impurities.

4.4 Volatile impurities

In addition to the pressure effect of the residual air, the triple-point temperature is increased above the ice point by about 2.5 mK due to the absence of the depressing effect of the dissolved gases. Thus for atmospheric gases, the effect of the dissolved gas is one third of the direct effect of pressure and, therefore, for most of MSL's cells can be ignored [15]. The effect does however depend on the species of the gases. Pure CO_2 , with a solubility 13 times that of air, gives rise to an error about four times that due to the pressure effect. It is assumed that the effect of dissolved gases is negligible.

4.5 Non-volatile ionic impurities

For ionic impurities, the impurity is manifest as an increase in the conductivity of the water. By using the cell as the dielectric in a large capacitor, the conductivity can be detected by measuring dielectric loss of the capacitor. This is a technique adapted by NML [16] to analyse water-triple-point cells. Figure 6 shows a diagram of the coaxial capacitor system set up by MSL to measure the conductivity of TPW cells. The coaxial system has the advantage of reducing a frequency dependent geometric correction that accounts for the frequency dependent propagation of the electric field into the water, which simplifies the model of the cell capacitance versus frequency. The lumped parameter model of the capacitor with a cell included is shown in Figure 7, and Figure 8 shows the measured capacitance versus frequency for a cell.

Figure 6: A simple schematic diagram of the capacitor used to evaluate the conductivity of the water in MSL's cells.

Figure 7: A simplified lumped parameter model of the coaxial capacitor used by MSL for the measurement of impurities in TPW cells. C_g represents the capacitance of the space between the surface of the water and the electrodes, and therefore includes the effect of an air gap and the glass of the triple point cell. C_w and R_w represent the capacitance due to the water in the cell and the resistance due to the conductivity of the water, respectively.

Figure 8: The measured capacitance versus frequency for a TPW cell (the marked points) and the capacitance as determined from a least-squares fit of the model of Figure 7 to the data. At low frequencies the capacitance is almost constant. At the turnover frequency (near 10 kHz in this case) the capacitance falls as the impedance of C_w becomes less than that of R_w . The turn over frequency $f_0 = (2\pi R_w C_w)^{-1}$ is a direct measure of the conductivity of the water, and in this case is about 8.7 kHz.

The model of Figure 7 leads to a frequency dependent capacitance for the cell of:

$$C_{\text{eff}}(\omega) = \frac{C_g C_w (f_0^2 + f^2)}{C_w f_0^2 + (C_g + C_w) f^2}, \quad (12)$$

where $f_0 = (2\pi R_w C_w)^{-1}$. Because the capacitor apparatus and TPW cell provide the same geometric definition for the cell capacitance and the conductance, the $R_w C_w$ time constant, or equivalently the turn-over frequency f_0 as shown in Figure 8, is independent of the geometry of the cell and measurement system and provides a direct measure of the conductivity of the water according to:

$$f_0 = \frac{1000\Lambda m}{2\pi\epsilon_w\epsilon_0}, \quad (13)$$

where ϵ_w is the dielectric constant for water, ϵ_0 is the permittivity of free space, and Λ is the molal conductivity ($\text{S}\cdot\text{m}^2\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$) of the ionic species. Knowledge of Λ for the impurity allows a determination of m and hence in combination with Equation (10) leads to the proportionality constant between the turn-over frequency and the temperature depression for the cell. Ballico suggested that a typical value of Λ is about $10 \text{ mS}\cdot\text{m}^2\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ leading to a sensitivity of $0.84 \mu\text{K}/\text{kHz}$, so the system is extremely sensitive. However, there are two complications. One is due to the low molal conductivity of some solutes and the other, the fact that the concentration varies with the frozen fraction of water in the TPW cell.

The Glass Engineering Handbook [19] and recent work by Hill [17,18] suggest that at least some of the impurities in TPW cells are due to dissolved glass. The concentrations of various impurities are strongly correlated with the composition of the Borosilcate glass typically used for TPW cells. Hill concluded that the effect may cause a TPW cell to drift by as much as $4 \mu\text{K}/\text{year}$, although there is a substantial variation in observed drift rates with some cells showing little drift over 40 years. Figure 9 shows the range of conductivities measured with MSL's conductivity apparatus for all of MSL's cells. The graph shows that the rate of increase in the conductivity of the cells is between 0.5 kHz and 1.5 kHz per year. The graph also shows that the conductivity of new cells is close to the theoretical value for pure water, 0.89 kHz .

Since the conductivity of the water increases with age it can be assumed that the main source of ionic impurity is the slow dissolution of the glass. This is consistent with the observations of Hill and with the known properties of borosilicate glass. Thus, an estimate of the value of Λ can be made assuming the impurities are derived entirely from glass.

Figure 9: The range of turnover frequencies for MSL's triple point of water cells versus the age of the cells.

If it is assumed that the sum of the molalities of the various impurities is equal to m and that the impurities are present in fractions k_i , then the total temperature depression is

$$\Delta T = \frac{2\pi\varepsilon_w\varepsilon_0K_f}{1000\sum\Lambda_i k_i} f_0. \quad (14)$$

The glass typically used for triple-point cells is a borosilicate glass composed of oxides of silicon, boron, aluminium and sodium with the composition as shown in Table 1. In solution, the oxides form acids and hydroxides, some of which dissociate. The main dissociation reactions are due to the sodium and the aluminium:

The process of dissolution of the glass probably begins with the dissolution of the sodium [20]. The ionisation of sodium (Equation (15)) increases the concentration of OH^- ions, which attack and dissolve the remaining constituents of the glass. Thus, the main contributors to the conductivity of the water are the Na^+ , OH^- , and AlO_2^- ions, with charge balance achieved as $[\text{Na}^+] = [\text{OH}^-] + [\text{AlO}_2^-]$. If it is assumed that the conductivities of the species are 5.01, 19.9, and 10 $\text{mS m}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$, respectively, then the conductivity of the solution of dissolved Borosilicate is 1.43 $\text{mS m}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$, and the sensitivity of the capacitor to impurities is 5.6 $\mu\text{K}/\text{kHz}$. The results of the calculations are summarised in Table 1.

Material	% by mass	Mol. Mass	Mol ions /100gm	Mol fraction	Conductivity $\text{mS m}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$	Conductivity \times Mol fraction
B_2O_3	13	69.62	0.37	0.189	0.0	0.00
Na_2O	4	61.98	0.12	0.065	5.0	0.33
Al_2O_3	2	101.96	0.04	0.020	10.0	0.20
SiO_2	81	60.09	1.35	0.681	0.0	0.00
(OH^-)			0.09	0.045	19.9	0.90
				Effective conductivity of soln.		1.43

Table 1: Summary of the calculation for the effective conductivity of a solution formed of the components of borosilicate glass dissolved in water.

The correlation between the observed increases in conductivity amongst MSL's cells ($\sim 1 \text{ kHz}/\text{yr}$) combined with this figure of 5.6 $\mu\text{K}/\text{kHz}$ and Hill's determination that cells drift about 4 $\mu\text{K}/\text{yr}$ is quite good considering the assumptions involved.

In practice, the effect of the dissolved glass may not be as significant as 5.6 $\mu\text{K}/\text{kHz}$ because at concentrations in excess of 10^{-8} molal, the aluminate tends to precipitate as Gibbsite, $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ [21]. Thus, the concentration of the impurities is probably less than suggested by this calculation. MSL's cells that are allowed to settle for several months do contain a very thin grey smear of particulate material of unknown origin at the bottom of the cell; this may be Gibbsite.

Based on this analysis it will be assumed that the temperature depression of the cells is $5.6 \mu\text{K}/\text{kHz}$ with a standard uncertainty of $2 \mu\text{K}/\text{kHz}$.

4.6 Non-volatile non-ionic impurities

Non-ionic impurities have the same effect as the ionic impurities, but are unfortunately difficult to detect within a sealed cell. During the manufacturing of TPW cells, as much as is practical MSL avoids contamination with sources of organic solutes such as would come from vacuum greases, rubber tubing, and some de-ionising plants. There have, however, been no tests to measure the possible concentration of such impurities. It has been observed, however, that two cells, because of a combination of events had most of their water degassed for a longer period than normal (more than 1 day compared to the usual $\frac{1}{2}$ day period). These cells appear to have a temperature about $20 \mu\text{K}$ above that of other cells once isotopic effects and glass impurity effects have been accounted for. This perhaps indicates that an extended degassing period may reduce the effects of these impurities by about $20 \mu\text{K}$.

It is assumed that MSL's cells are on average $10 \mu\text{K}$ below ideal due to non-volatile non-ionic impurities. The typical range is estimated to be from zero to $20 \mu\text{K}$ with a relative uncertainty of about 50% ($\nu = 2$) in the upper value.

5 Instrumental Effects

5.1 Background

It is one thing to have realised the triple-point temperature, quite another to measure the temperature or compare the realisation of different cells. Factors affecting any measurement of the triple-point temperature include effects due to the SPRT and the resistance bridge [22].

5.2 SPRT stability

The measurement of the resistance $R(0.01 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}, 0 \text{ mA})$ of the SPRT typically takes about 1 hour. It involves the thermal settling time for the SPRT and the TPW cell after the SPRT is immersed, and the time to take the three measurements $R(1 \text{ mA})$, $R(\sqrt{2} \text{ mA})$, and $R(1 \text{ mA})$.

It is notable that some SPRTs are better than others in respect of stability. A significant factor seems to be the migration of moisture within the SPRT sheath, and the amount of stress and strain introduced with the movement of the SPRT between different measuring situations. The observed effects may be as large as $50 \mu\text{K}$, but in most cases are not detectable at the level of about $10 \mu\text{K}$.

It is assumed that where the effect is critical to the outcome of a measurement the SPRT will be selected for stability, and the measurement will be repeated using a sequence that allows any bias to be eliminated and the resulting uncertainty to be measured.

5.3 Self heating

Each time a TPW measurement is made and corrected to 0 mA it is assumed that during the three measurements at different currents, the self heating coefficient for the SPRT and cell remains constant. For most measurements this appears to be the case, since the first and last of the three measurements are very similar.

However it has been noticed that for any one cell and SPRT, the range of self-heating corrections does vary. Figure 10 shows the range of self-heating corrections for five of MSL's TPW cells. Cell 96/1 was a special cell made with a large diameter thermometer well to accommodate industrial PRTs. The remaining 4 cells all have the same nominal diameter. The distribution of self-heating corrections shows two main features: a dependence on cell geometry and variability larger than can be accounted for by other mechanisms.

The variability of the self-heating correction presumably depends on factors relating to the thermal coupling between the SPRT and the ice-water interface within the cell. This must depend on the thickness of the layer of water between the cell and the ice, the amount of water in the thermometer well, and the position of the SPRT within the well.

It is noted that some NMIs recommend the use of an aluminium or copper sleeve to centre the thermometer in the well and provide better thermal conductivity than water alone. The use of a collet to centre the SPRT at the top of the well may also be useful. Note that the sponge used primarily to provide mechanical protection for the thermometer and TPW cell also provides immunity against buoyancy effects so should be retained in all measurements.

It is assumed that where the variation in self heating is critical to the outcome of a measurement, the measurement will be repeated using a sequence that allows any bias to be eliminated and the resulting uncertainty to be measured.

Figure 10: The range of self heating observed with a series of comparisons of TPW cells. The self-heating measurements are sorted according to cell ID then according to increasing value of the self-heating correction.

5.4 Bridge noise

Noise in the resistance measurements arises from several sources including the thermal noise in the resistors, thermal noise in the resistors and amplifiers of the bridge circuitry, and electromagnetic interference. It is assumed that the noise is purely random so does not bias the measurements.

It has been noted (NML private communication) that a pair of ac bridges operating at the same carrier frequency in the same vicinity can have signals that are coupled. This effect does bias measurements.

5.5 Standard resistor variations

The bridge reading is the ratio of the unknown resistance to the resistance of a standard resistor, typically a 25 Ω or 100 Ω Wilkins style resistor. These are maintained in a temperature controlled bath with a short term stability of about 5 mK r.m.s and a long term average stability of better than ± 1 mK. Since the resistors have temperature coefficients of about 3 ppm/ $^{\circ}\text{C}$, the effects are below 10 μK . Further, on average over many measurements the effects should be random and contribute to the observed variance in the measurements.

5.6 Bridge non-linearity

Bridge non-linearity, is usually a mix of differential non-linearity and integral non-linearity. The significance of the effects of the non-linearities depends on the application. When establishing a temperature scale the effects of both types of bridge non-linearities are relatively minor [22].

When measuring small temperature differences, such as with fixed-point comparisons and self-heating corrections, the effects of integral non-linearity are negligible, but differential non-linearities (DNL) can have a significant effect. The analysis of experimental results given in [22] suggests that differential non-linearities may be of the order of 2×10^{-8} r.m.s in bridge readings (20 μK r.m.s. for 25 Ω SPRT), but there has been no direct evidence for DNL published.

Direct evidence for DNL in MSL's ASL F18 bridge is shown in Figure 11, a freeze plateau for an indium point realisation. The intriguing feature of the graph is the lack of measurement points immediately below the horizontal gridlines. This is particularly apparent in the vicinity of 18 hrs. Figure 12 plots a histogram of the bridge readings between 14 and 22 hrs. Here it is apparent that the frequency of readings of 0.410 684 09 are very low compared to neighbouring readings that should have a similar frequency. Similarly the 0.410 684 10 readings are rather more frequent than expected. Such differences in frequency would be exactly as expected with large differential non-linearity occurring at the code transition from 0.XXX XXX 09 to 0.XXX XXX 10 in a bridge based on decimal dividers. That a similar effect occurs adjacent to the one upper and two lower gridlines in Figure 11, further suggests that the effect is due to a base 10 DNL.

Figure 11: A plot of an Indium point realisation exhibiting differential non-linearity in the bridge readings. Each vertical division marked corresponds to approximately 100 μ K.

Figure 12: A histogram of the readings in Figure 9 between 50 000 and 80 000 seconds highlighting the low frequency of readings ending in 9 and the high frequency of readings ending in 0.

The effects of the DNL error depend on the nature of the error. If, as suggested in Figure 12, the low frequency of readings ending in 9 is balanced by the high frequency of readings ending in 0, then there will be a small bias in averaged readings. If the low frequency of readings ending in 9 were not balanced by the readings ending in 0 then all readings over a wide range may be biased. DNL errors may also be amplified by extrapolation processes, such as the self-heating correction.

For the purposes of the comparisons of temperatures, i.e. measurements of temperature differences, it is assumed that the DNL errors introduce errors similar to quantisation error, so therefore contribute to the uncertainty but on average do not bias readings.

5.7 Bridge current ratios

In making the self-heating corrections it is assumed that the ratio of the sensing currents is exactly $\sqrt{2}$. Uncertainties in the current ratio propagate to uncertainties in the triple-point temperature. Since the resistance at any current is

$$R(I) = R(0 \text{ mA})(1 + RI^2\alpha s), \quad (17)$$

where s is the self heating constant, α is the temperature coefficient of the resistance, and I the sensing current. When the zero-current resistance is estimated as

$$\begin{aligned} R(0 \text{ mA}) &= R(1 \text{ mA}) - R(\sqrt{2} \text{ mA}) + R(0 \text{ mA}) \\ &= R(0 \text{ mA}) \left[1 + \alpha s R I_1^2 \left(2 - \frac{I_2^2}{I_1^2} \right) \right] \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

errors in the current ratios cause an error in the estimate of the zero current resistance. Hence the temperature uncertainties in the current ratio $\rho = I_1/I_2$ propagate as

$$u_T = \alpha s R I_1^2 2\rho u_\rho.$$

Thus for a 1.5 mK self heating error, the uncertainty in the current ratio must be less than 0.025% to give rise to an uncertainty of less than 1 μ K. This is the case at present for the MSL F18 bridge, so the uncertainty contribution will be ignored.

5.8 Perturbing heat influences

We have carried out three tests for perturbing heat influences.

The immersion profile for the SPRT (Figure 2), as it is increasingly immersed in the cell, should show a slope corresponding to the hydrostatic pressure correction. With MSL's cells, which are larger than most, there appears to be at least 50 mm to 100 mm of excess immersion suggesting that heat leaks up the stem of the thermometer are negligible.

Routinely, the triple-point cells are maintained in self-draining dewars containing shaved ice. The lid to the dewar has a hole slightly larger than the SPRT handle to allow the lid to be in place when the cell is in use. A black velvet cloth is used to cover the handle to prevent light from penetrating the cell. No change in temperature is observed when the cloth is removed.

In the cells manufactured by MSL, the thermometer well extends several centimetres above the top of the triple-point cell. This allows ice to be placed around the top of the cell to cool the top of the SPRT. When this is done, or when the depth of the layer of ice over the cell is increased, no change in temperature is observed.

A fourth factor, not considered to date, is the possibility of convection within the water surrounding the SPRT in the thermometer well. It has been suggested [Dean Ripple, NIST] that the reason that the measured hydrostatic immersion profile usually has a slightly higher slope than theory (see Figure 2 and 5) is due to convection. It is apparently worse in larger diameter thermometer wells. NIST advise that an aluminium sleeve around the sensor near the bottom of the well eliminates the effect. It is assumed that when fully immersed the SPRT suppresses the convection.

The uncertainty due to perturbing heat exchanges is assumed to be zero.

6 Summary of Uncertainties

Table 2 summarises all of the uncertainties associated with the realisation of the triple point of water using the MSL 01/02 cell, which was used for the transfer cell for the CCT-K7 comparison in 2002. Note that the instrumentation effects associated with the measurement of the triple point temperature (immersion, radiation effects, time constants, bridge errors, self heating, SPRT instability) have been omitted. Table 3 summarises the uncertainty for the five MSL cells for which the isotopic composition is known.

Origin of effect	Standard uncertainty	(Effective) degrees of freedom
	(μK)	
Isotopic composition	0.5	100
Isotopic fractionation	1	100
Hydrostatic pressure	2	100
Residual gas pressure	0	-
Dissolved gases	0	-
Dissolved glass impurities	1	100
Crystal defects, etc	5	100
Other impurity	6	2
Total	8.2	6.9

Table 2: Uncertainty for cell MSL 01/02. A summary of the uncertainty contributions in a realisation of the temperature of the triple point of water. The number of degrees of freedom associated for each uncertainty is assigned values of 100 (most cases) to indicate the high confidence in the uncertainty. The exception is that associated with the non-volatile non-ionic impurity which is accordingly assigned a value of 2.

Cell ID	Date of manufacture	Isotopic depression / μ K	Impurity depression / μ K	$T_{\text{cell}} - 273.16 \text{ K}$ / μ K	Standard uncertainty / μ K	Expanded uncertainty / μ K (95%)
MSL 01/02	11 April 2001	-39.6	-12.8	-52	8.2	19
MSL 01/04	3 April 2001	-49.1	-13.1	-62	8.2	19
MSL 01/06	13 June 2001	-58.0	-18.2	-76	8.6	20
MSL 96/1	29 July 1996	-69.3	-45.7	-115	15.1	30
MSL 96/4	9 August 1996	-28.0	-30.8	-59	11.0	23

Table 3: Summary of the corrections and uncertainties for MSL's five reference cells at November 2002.

The total uncertainty in the realisation of the triple point for the purpose of calibrating an SPRT is dominated by the uncertainty due to bridge non-linearities and noise. The total expanded uncertainty is typically of the order of 50 μ K

When used for differential measurements, such as the comparison of triple-point cells the uncertainty is dominated by the variance due to impurities, isotopic fractionation, buoyancy pressure variations, hydrostatic head variations, variations in the temperature of the standard resistor, and crystal defects. All of these cause irreproducibility in the triple point temperature and are manifest as Type A uncertainties in the experimental measurements of difference. In extended measurements, such as those for CCT-K7, the Type A standard uncertainty is 4 μ K ($\nu=2$), corresponding to an expanded uncertainty in the differences of 17 μ K.

7 Evidence of Performance

Supporting evidence for the quality of MSL's TPW cells comes directly from two international comparisons and from a comparison of MSL's five reference cells. Figure 13 shows a summary of the results from the BIPM comparison of triple point of water cells completed in June 1996. Figure 14 show the results of a comparison with NIST conducted as part of the study of isotopic composition of TPW cells. All of the measurements carried out in the comparisons are corrected for the hydrostatic head, but not for isotopic composition or impurities.

Figure 13: Summary of the 1996 BIPM comparison of triple point of water cells [23]. An uncertainty of 40 μK ($k=2$) was assigned by the BIPM as an overall assessment of the uncertainty in the difference measurements.

Figure 14: Summary of triple point of water comparisons with NIST as a part of the isotope study [3]. Cell 96/1 was manufactured from local tap water - a 'normal' MSL cell, 96/2 is water from the Barne Glacier, 96/3 is water from Lake Vanda, and 96/4 is frozen sea water. The uncertainties indicated are the Type A assessments (1σ) based on the last five difference measurements made for the cell, and vary between 4 μK and 9 μK . The indices C1-C4 indicate the group of measurements conducted by NIST.

Because all of the effects given above (except the hydrostatic head effect) tend to decrease the TPW temperature, the cells that are highest on the graphs tend to be the best, having fewer impurities and less isotopic depletion. In particular, it is known that the NIST cells were manufactured by Jarrett (now owned and operated by Isotech) and are believed to be made in a continuous distillation process that tends to produce a low level of isotopic fractionation. These are the highest performing cells in both comparisons.

The BIPM comparison shows that the MSL cells are amongst the group of the best cells, although the uncertainties in the differences are a little large to draw firm conclusions about the size of the difference. The results of the NIST comparison have very low uncertainties and indicate that the MSL cells are about $55 \mu\text{K} \pm 5 \mu\text{K}$ below

the Jarrett cells. This is as would be expected with $\sim 40 \mu\text{K}$ due to isotopic fractionation in MSL's manufacturing plus a small amount for the difference between tropical and temperate surface water. Note also that the seawater cell (96/4) is $20 \mu\text{K}$ higher than the normal cell.

Figure 15 summarises the results of the comparison between MSL's five reference cells. The zero in the graph corresponds to the average of the five corrected temperatures, and is defined by MSL to be 273.16 K . The graph shows the dispersion of results to be consistent with the results of the uncertainty analysis.

Figure 15: Comparison of the measured temperature differences between MSLs five reference cells. The measured temperatures were corrected for isotopic composition and impurities as indicated in Table 3. The uncertainties indicated in the figure are the standard uncertainties indicated in Table 3.

8 Notes on Technique

- Use a sponge in the thermometer well. The sponge will provide some protection from mechanical damage for the thermometer and the triple-point cell if the thermometer is dropped. However the main benefit is elimination of the buoyancy pressure effect (Section 3.4). The sponge should be about 10 mm long.
- Ensure that the mantle is freed properly from the thermometer well. The pressure against the well will lower the temperature at this point and make the temperature less reproducible.
- Measure the hydrostatic head when the cell is frozen. Because of the differences in the density of ice and water, the head will change with frozen fraction.
- For highest accuracy work use the Meyers design SPRT. This has a lower self-heating effect, and shorter measurement time.
- For highest accuracy, use the Hart 'quickstick' heat-pipe cooler to form the mantle wait at least 5 days for the ice mantle to anneal.
- For the highest accuracy work use a cell with the lowest impurity effect (MSL 01/02 currently).
- The SPRT should not be moved from its position in the thermometer well during the sequence of $R(1 \text{ mA})$, $R(\sqrt{2} \text{ mA})$, and $R(1 \text{ mA})$ measurements.

- To maintain a constant and low value of self heating, an aluminium sleeve surrounding the SPRT sensor may be useful, and a collet in the neck of the cell will help locate the SPRT.

9 Conclusions

The cells manufactured by MSL, corrected for isotopic composition and corrected for impurities will realize the triple point temperature with an uncertainty of about 20 μK to 30 μK . Cells with an age of less than 5 years should be used for highest accuracy work to reduce the uncertainty in the impurity corrections.

A major factor in the reduction in uncertainty achieved since the last full analysis (accompanying the 1996 BIPM comparison) is due to three factors:

- The measurement and application of corrections for isotopic composition
- The measurement of the conductivity of the water in the cells using Ballico's method, and hence the identification of good cells.
- The application of impurity corrections based on the conductivity measurements.

A large part of the uncertainty in the impurity correction arises from the uncertainty in the propriety of the model. It seems likely that cells manufactured from quartz may exhibit reduced drift rates due to the low solubility of pure silica. More research is required in this area.

The buoyancy pressure effects appear to be more significant than previously thought. The biggest benefit of the sponge in the thermometer well may be thermal isolation from the effect. It may be that flat bottomed thermometer wells are also less susceptible. More research is required in this area.

In the manufacture of triple point of water cells [24], the degassing phase should be extended from $\frac{1}{2}$ day to 2 days. It was observed in the comparison of the five reference cells that the two that had been degassed for an extended period appeared to realise a temperature about 20 μK higher than the other three cells.

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